

Growth and Yield Response of Sweet Corn (*Zea mays* var. *Saccharata* Sturt.) at Various Doses of Ammonium Sulfate Fertilizer

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ABSTRACT

Sweet corn is a horticultural commodity that is widely cultivated and consumed in Indonesia. This study aimed to determine the growth and yield response of sweet corn plants to the application of various doses of ammonium sulfate fertilizer. The research was conducted at Pasir Kuda Experimental Field, Bogor, West Java. This experiment used a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with a single factor, namely the dose of fertilizer application. Treatments were arranged in 4 levels of application, namely: (1) control, (2) standard NPK fertilization, (3) 0.5 dose of N, (4) 1,0 doses of N, (5) 1,5 doses of N, and (6) 2,0 doses of N. The results of this test indicate that the application level of ammonium sulfate fertilizers at the application level of 1,0 doses N fertilizer treatment can generally provide plant height, stem diameter, number of leaves, stover weight, cob weight with husk, cob weight without husk, production plot¹, and productivity which are statistically higher than the control treatment. The application of 1,0 doses N fertilizer treatment had Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE) values that meet the requirements to pass the fertilizer effectiveness test, with the highest RAE value obtained in the application of 1,0 doses N fertilizer at 188%.

Keywords: *fertilizer effectiveness, inorganic fertilizer, nutrient management, productivity, sweet corn cultivation*

INTRODUCTION

Plants can grow and develop and produce maximum yields if supported by good soil conditions that provide nutrients for the plants. Optimal plant growth requires nutrients to be present in optimal amounts and concentrations and to be in balance in the soil (Shedley *et al.*, 2008). One important factor that determines plant growth and development is fertilization. In general, fertilization is the addition of substances to the soil with the aim of improving or increasing soil fertility, while fertilization in a specific sense is the addition of substances intended to increase plant nutrients in the soil. Plants need macro and micro nutrients to grow and produce well, while intensively cultivated soil is generally no longer able to meet all of the plant's nutrient requirements. Fertilization is needed to meet plant requirements. The optimum fertilization dose for plants depends on the soil's ability to provide nutrients (soil nutrient status) and the expected yield.

Macro nutrients are needed in greater quantities than micro nutrients. Macro nutrients play an active role in plant metabolism. The main macro nutrients required by plants are N, P, and K. Nitrogen is one of the most common and widely needed nutrients during the vegetative phase of plants. Nitrogen is mobile in the soil, making it prone to loss through leaching and evaporation (Namohaji *et al.*, 2022). About 60-70% of N loss is caused by volatilization and denitrification of NO_3 (Dobermann and Fairhurst, 2000). N deficiency is a problem often experienced by farmers. Nitrogen is the main component of amino acids, which function as protein building blocks (Marschner, 2012). In addition, N also plays a major role as a component of chlorophyll, the green pigment in plants that enables photosynthesis. Sufficient N availability in plants allows them to reach their genetic yield potential. However, excessive N fertilization will increase vegetative growth and shorten the generative period, which will ultimately reduce yield (Astuti *et al.*, 2018).

Sulfur (S) is an essential macronutrient required for optimal plant growth, development, and yield. Although needed in smaller amounts compared to nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K), sulfur plays a crucial role in numerous physiological and biochemical processes. Sulfur is a fundamental component of amino acids such as cysteine and methionine, which are building blocks of proteins, and it contributes to the formation of coenzymes, vitamins (biotin and thiamine), and secondary metabolites such as glucosinolates (Hawkesford, 2014). Adequate sulfur nutrition enhances chlorophyll synthesis, photosynthetic activity, and the efficiency of nitrogen utilization, thereby improving overall crop productivity (Scherer, 2009; Haneklaus *et al.*, 2017).

Sulfur deficiency has emerged as a widespread nutrient disorder in agricultural systems. Historically, atmospheric deposition from industrial emissions supplied sufficient sulfur to soils. However, reductions in sulfur emissions due to air quality regulations, coupled with intensive cropping systems and the use of high-analysis fertilizers with little or no sulfur, have led to widespread sulfur depletion in soils (Zhao *et al.*, 1999; McGrath and Zhao, 1996). Sulfur deficiency is particularly evident in coarse-textured soils with low organic matter and high rainfall regions where sulfate leaching was occurred (Camberato and Casteel, 2017). The purpose of study was to determine the growth and yield response of sweet corn plants to the application of various doses of ammonium sulfate fertilizer.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out at the IPB Pasir Kuda Experimental Field, Bogor Regency, West Java, from September to December 2024. The plant material used was sweet corn (*Zea mays* var. *saccharata* Sturt.) of the Exotic variety, while the fertilizers applied included ammonium sulfate (21% N, 24% S), urea, SP-36, and KCl. The equipment used consisted of common cultivation tools, measuring instruments, as well as a camera and stationery. The study was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with four replications. The treatment factor was the application of calcium nitrate fertilizer at six levels: (1) control, (2) standard NPK fertilization, (3) 0.5 dose of N, (4) 1,0 doses of N, (5) 1,5 doses of N, and (6) 2,0 doses of N, resulting in 24 experimental units. Each experimental plot measured 5 × 5 m.

The standard NPK fertilizer doses for N, P, and K requirements of sweet corn were 135 kg N ha⁻¹, 72 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹, and 120 kg K₂O ha⁻¹, equivalent to 300 kg urea ha⁻¹, 200 kg SP-36 ha⁻¹, and 200 kg KCl ha⁻¹. The nutrient content of standard NPK fertilizer (NPK- std) used were urea (45% N), SP-36 (36% P₂O₅), and KCl (60% K₂O), which have been previously validated for their effectiveness. The detailed treatment structure is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Details of inorganic calcium nitrate fertilizer treatment

Treatment	Ammonium Sulfate (kg ha ⁻¹)	Urea (kg ha ⁻¹)	SP-36 (kg ha ⁻¹)	KCl (kg ha ⁻¹)
P0 (Control)	0	0	200	200
P1 (NPK standard)	0	300	200	200
P2 (0,5 N)	321	0	200	200
P3 (1,0 N)	643	0	200	200
P4 (1,5 N)	964	0	200	200
P5 (2,0 N)	1.286	0	200	200

Land preparation was carried out by hoeing the soil to a depth of approximately 25 cm, followed by exposure to direct sunlight. Sweet corn was planted by making holes with a dibble at a spacing of 75 cm × 20 cm. Two seeds were sown per hole together with an insecticide containing the active ingredient carbofuran. At two weeks after planting (WAP), seedlings were thinned to maintain one plant per hole. SP-36 fertilizer was applied entirely at planting, while urea and KCl in the standard NPK treatment and also ammonium sulfate fertilizer was applied in two equal splits: at planting and at 4 WAP.

Observations were conducted on both vegetative growth and yield components. Growth parameters, including plant height, number of leaves, and stem diameter, were measured at 4, 6, and 8 WAP using 10 sample plants per experimental plot. Harvesting was conducted at approximately 10 weeks after planting. Yield-related measurements included fresh weight of the aboveground biomass, cob weight with husk, and cob weight without husk, also using 10 sample plants per plot. In addition, all filled cobs from the net

plot area (excluding border plants) were harvested, weighed, and converted to estimate crop productivity.

Agronomic performance was further evaluated using the Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE) index. Inorganic fertilizer treatments were considered effective if their performance was statistically comparable or superior to the standard fertilizer treatment, or significantly better than the control at the 5% level. Fertilizers with RAE values $\geq 95\%$ were regarded as agronomically effective (Machay *et al.*, 1984). The RAE was calculated using the formula:

$$RAE = \frac{\text{corn productivity from tested fertilizers} - \text{control}}{\text{corn productivity from comparison fertilizer} - \text{control}} \times 100\%$$

All collected data were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the F-test in SAS software. When significant differences were detected, mean separation was performed using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at a 5% significance level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Conditions of Experiment

The nutrient analysis of the ammonium sulfate fertilizer was conducted at the beginning of the study to determine its nutrient composition. The results of the nutrient analysis of the inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer used in this experiment were presented in Table 2. The test results showed that the N content was 21,02%, S 24,93%, H₂SO₄ 0,07%, and water content 0,20%.

Table 2. Analysis results of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Testing Parameters	Unit	Test Results
N	%	21,02
S	%	24,93
H ₂ SO ₄	%	0,07
Water content	%	0,20

Soil analysis was conducted prior to the experiment by collecting samples from all treatment plots and compositing them. The soil test aimed to determine the fertility status of the experimental field before treatment application. The results of the soil analysis are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Soil analysis results before the experiment

Parameter	Unit	Value	Category*
pH H ₂ O	-	5,40	Sour
C-organic	%	1,55	Low
N-total	%	0,20	Low
P-available (Bray I)	ppm P ₂ O ₅	46,50	Very High
CEC	cmol kg ⁻¹	12,88	Low

K-dd cmol K kg⁻¹ 1,00 Very High

*Source: *Balittanah* (2023)

The analysis of variance indicated that the treatments applied had no significant effect on growth components (plant height, stem diameter, number of leaves) and fresh biomass weight, cob weight with husk, and cob weight without husk but significantly influenced yield components including production plot⁻¹, and productivity of sweet corn. The coefficients of variation (CV) for growth components ranged from 7,79–11,06% for plant height, 6,20–9,40% for stem diameter, 7,93–18,14% for the number of leaves, and 15,87% for fresh biomass weight. Meanwhile, the CV values for yield components ranged from 9,74–11,13%, with the lowest CV observed in cob weight without husk, and the highest in production plot⁻¹ and productivity (Table 4).

Table 4. Recapitulation of analysis variance of the effect of inorganic ammonium sulfate on growth and yield components of sweet corn

Variable	Treatment	Coefficient of Variance (%)
Growth components:		
Plant height		
4 WAP	tn	11,06
6 WAP	tn	8,21
8 WAP	tn	7,79
Stem diameter		
4 WAP	tn	6,56
6 WAP	tn	9,40
8 WAP	tn	6,20
Number of leaves		
4 WAP	tn	18,14
6 WAP	tn	8,85
8 WAP	tn	7,93
Stover weight	tn	15,87
Yield components:		
Cob weight with husk	tn	10,18
Cob weight without husk	tn	9,74
Production plot ⁻¹	**	11,33
Productivity	**	11,33

Description: *Significant at $\alpha=5\%$ level, ** Significant at $\alpha=1\%$ level, tn=Not Significant

The Effect of Inorganic Ammonium Sulfate Fertilizer on Sweet Corn Growth Components

The results of the analysis showed that fertilizer treatments had no significant effect on plant height from 4 to 8 weeks after planting (WAP) (Table 5). The mean plant

height ranged from 72,53–82,50 cm (4 WAP), 159,98–174,88 cm (6 WAP), and 168,43–184,28 cm (8 WAP). However, the application of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer (treatment P3) consistently produced taller plants compared to the control across all observation periods.

Table 5. Plant height at different application rates of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Treatment	Plant height (cm)		
	4 WAP	6 WAP	8 WAP
P0 (Control)	72,53a	159,98a	168,43a
P1 (NPK standard)	75,03a	165,60a	176,83a
P2 (0,5 N)	78,65a	165,98a	178,63a
P3 (1,0 N)	82,50a	174,88a	184,28a
P4 (1,5 N)	74,33a	162,68a	173,10a
P5 (2,0 N)	74,15a	167,13a	176,38a

Description: a,b,c,d,e number followed by different letters in the same column indicate significant differences based on the results of DMRT α 5% test.

Similarly, treatment P3 resulted in a higher number of leaves than the control from 4 to 8 WAP (Table 6). The mean number of leaves ranged from 6,23-6,80 (4 WAP), 8,83–10,00 (6 WAP), and 11,15–13,10 (8 WAP), Nevertheless, statistical analysis indicated that fertilizer treatments had no significant effect on leaf number across these growth stages (Table 6).

Table 6. Number of leaves at different application rates of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Treatment	Number of leaves		
	4 WAP	6 WAP	8 WAP
P0 (Control)	6,40a	8,83a	11,15a
P1 (NPK standard)	6,45a	9,08a	12,48a
P2 (0,5 N)	6,63a	9,73a	12,58a
P3 (1,0 N)	6,80a	9,90a	13,10a
P4 (1,5 N)	6,23a	9,90a	12,43a
P5 (2,0 N)	6,33a	10,00a	12,50a

Description: a,b,c,d,e number followed by different letters in the same column indicate significant differences based on the results of DMRT α 5% test.

The analysis presented in Table 7 shows that all doses of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer had no significant effect on stem diameter from 4 to 8 weeks after planting (WAP). The mean stem diameter ranged from 14,65-17,36 mm (4 WAP), 20,98-23,05 mm (6 WAP), and 22,44-25,10 mm (8 WAP) (Table 7).

Table 7. Stem diameter at different application rates of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Treatment	Stem diameter (mm)		
	4 WAP	6 WAP	8 WAP
P0 (Control)	14,65a	20,98a	22,44a
P1 (NPK standard)	15,51a	22,65a	24,35a
P2 (0,5 N)	17,36a	22,49a	24,10a
P3 (1,0 N)	16,04a	22,31a	25,10a
P4 (1,5 N)	15,96a	21,38a	23,90a
P5 (2,0 N)	16,62a	23,05a	25,00a

Description: a,b,c,d,e number followed by different letters in the same column indicate significant differences based on the results of DMRT α 5% test.

Effect of Inorganic Ammonium Sulfate Fertilizer on Sweet Corn Yield Components

The analysis showed that the application of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer had no significant effect on stover weight, cob weight with husk, and cob weight without husk ($p < 0.05$) (Table 8). The mean stover weight ranged from 4,79 - 5,85 kg, while the mean cob weight with husk and cob weight without husk ranged from 290,87 - 370,95 g and 223,93 - 277,88 g, respectively (Table 8).

Table 8. Observations result of yield components and stover weight at various levels of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Treatment	Stover weight (kg)	Cob weight with husk (g)	Cob weight without husk (g)
P0 (Control)	4,79a	290,87a	223,93a
P1 (NPK standard)	5,23a	360,54a	272,85a
P2 (0,5 N)	5,45a	362,48a	270,06a
P3 (1,0 N)	5,85a	370,95a	277,88a
P4 (1,5 N)	5,08a	342,30a	256,34a
P5 (2,0 N)	5,38a	354,98a	264,46a

Description: a,b,c,d,e number followed by different letters in the same column indicate significant differences based on the results of DMRT α 5% test.

Further analysis of production plot⁻¹ and productivity revealed highly significant effects of fertilizer treatments (Table 9). The mean production plot⁻¹ ranged from 9,46 – 17,82 kg, while productivity ranged from 8,09 – 15,2 tons ha⁻¹ (Table 9). Treatments with ammonium sulfate fertilizer (P2–P5) produced significantly higher yields compared to the

control (P0), but were not significantly different from the standard fertilizer treatment (P1) in terms of both production plot⁻¹ and productivity.

Table 9. Production per plot and productivity at different treatment inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Treatment	Production plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Productivity (ton ha ⁻¹)
P0 (Control)	9.46 c	8.09 c
P1 (NPK standard)	13.92 b	11.9 b
P2 (0,5 N)	14.04 b	12.0 b
P3 (1,0 N)	17.82 a	15.2 a
P4 (1,5 N)	17.64 a	15.1 a
P5 (2,0 N)	16.87 a	14.4 a

Description: a,b,c,d,e number followed by different letters in the same column indicate significant differences based on the results of DMRT α 5% test.

Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE) is an indicator used to measure the effectiveness of a fertilizer. A fertilizer is considered effective when it achieves an RAE value of $\geq 95\%$, indicating that its yield improvement surpasses the relative increase obtained from the reference fertilizer compared to the control. The RAE values of inorganic calcium nitrate fertilizer are presented in Table 10.

The results showed that inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer was effective only when applied at 0,50 dose (P2), 1,0 dose (P3), 1,5 dose (P4), and 2,0 doses (P5). The highest effectiveness was observed at the 1,0 doses, with an RAE value of 188%. This indicates that the application of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer at the full dose increased yield 1,88 times higher than the improvement achieved by the reference fertilizer over the control (P0).

Table 10. Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE) valued at different application rates of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer

Treatment	RAE (%)
P0 (Control)	-
P1 (NPK standard)	-
P2 (0,5 N)	103
P3 (1,0 N)	188
P4 (1,5 N)	183
P5 (2,0 N)	166

N fertilizer plays an important role in increasing corn production. N nutrients are the main nutrients that make up chlorophyll, which plays an important role in the photosynthesis process in plants. Plants that lack N nutrients will have yellowing leaves, resulting in suboptimal photosynthesis. In addition, nitrogen also plays a role in the formation of amino acids, proteins, and components of the cell nucleus. Excessive

application of nitrogen fertilizer to corn plants can increase damage from pests and diseases, especially during the rainy season, prolong the life of the plant, and cause the plant to fall over more easily due to stems that are larger than normal, while the roots are unable to support them. Excessive use of fertilizer not only increases production costs but also damages the environment due to N_2O emissions during ammonification, nitrification, and denitrification (Wahid, 2003). Ammonium Sulfate fertilizer contains 24% sulphur (in the form of sulfate) and 21% nitrogen (in the form of ammonium). Its nitrogen content is only half that of urea, so it is usually applied as a source of sulphur in soils that are deficient in this element. Sulphur is one of the macro elements that plants need in large quantities because it is one of the main components of cell nuclei and an important element in protein formation (Miller and Donahue, 1990). The application of Ammonium Sulfate fertilizer increases the N and S content in plant tissues. When S is limited, the addition of nitrogen fertilizer does not change the yield and protein content in plants (Singh *et al.*, 2012).

The results of this study demonstrated that varying doses of inorganic ammonium sulfate had no significant effect on vegetative growth or yield components such as stover weight, cob weight with husked, and cob weight without husked of sweet corn. Nevertheless, the application of a full dose (643 kg ha^{-1} , P3) significantly increased production plot^{-1} and overall productivity compared to the control (P0) and standard NPK fertilizer treatment (P1).

The macro nutrient requirements of plants range from 0,12% to 3,6%. Among all macro nutrients, nitrogen is the most needed by plants, followed by potassium, calcium, phosphorus, and sulfur. Nitrogen is a macro nutrient that is needed in large quantities by plants (Kathpalia and Bhatla, 2018). Nitrogen is primarily needed to support the vegetative growth of plants. This is in line with field results that show a significant effect on sweet corn plants fertilized with Ammonium Sulfate compared to sweet corn plants that were not fertilized (control) in terms of plant height, number of leaves, and stem diameter. Optimal vegetative growth will support the yield growth of plants, followed by high production and productivity. Treatments with 0.5 to 2.0 doses of Ammonium Sulfate fertilizer produced sweet corn plot^{-1} ranging from 10,97 to 14,47 kg, with productivity based on area comparison (plot) of 8 to 10 tons ha^{-1} . This productivity value is better than the control treatment with a productivity of 6.65 tons ha^{-1} and is as good as the standard treatment, which produced a productivity of 8.59 tons ha^{-1} . The 1,0–2,0 doses of Ammonium Sulfate treatment has better productivity potential than the standard treatment. This is indicated by an RAE value > 95% in the 1,0–2,0 doses of Ammonium Sulfate treatment.

Ammonium sulfate fertilizer plays a role in increasing soil fertility, especially in soils deficient in N and S nutrients, and meets the needs of plants, especially for N and S nutrients. Ammonium sulfate fertilizer is generally (50%) widely used as a source of S nutrients (Powlson and Dawson, 2021). Ammonium sulfate fertilizer plays a role in plant metabolism, helping to form chlorophyll granules so that the leaves appear greener and improving the taste and aroma of shallots (Sutardjo and Pratiwa, 2010). The results of research by Saptorini *et al.* (2019) show that applying 400 kg ha^{-1} of Ammonium Sulfate fertilizer can increase plant height, number of leaves and number of bulbs, enlarge shallot

bulbs and reduce shrinkage during storage, as well as increase shallot bulb production to 12.11 tons ha⁻¹.

Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE) analysis confirmed the efficiency of calcium nitrate at a dose of 900 kg ha⁻¹, with an RAE value of 188%. An RAE above 100% indicates that the tested fertilizer not only matches but surpasses the yield improvement achieved with the reference fertilizer. These findings suggest that ammonium sulfate could serve as a potential substitute for urea in sweet corn cultivation, while simultaneously supplying essential N and S to optimize plant growth and productivity.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicated that the application of different doses of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer did not significant differences in the vegetative growth of sweet corn (plant height, stem diameter, and number of leaves) or in yield components (stover weight, cob weight with husk, and cob weight without husk) but significant differences in production plot⁻¹ and overall productivity. However, application of the full dose (1,0) of inorganic ammonium sulfate fertilizer produced a higher Relative Agronomic Effectiveness (RAE) compared to the reference treatment, reaching 188% or 1.88 times increase over the improvement achieved by the reference fertilizer relative to the control. Based on these findings, the recommended fertilizer dosage for sweet corn is 643 kg ha⁻¹ of inorganic calcium nitrate, supplemented with 200 kg ha⁻¹ of SP-36 and 200 kg ha⁻¹ of KCl.

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